

Primality test

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August 24, 2023

An idea to test the primality of a number:

$$isPrime(n) = mod(2^n - 1) = 1 \quad AND \quad mod((n - 1)!, n) \neq 0$$

An idea to test the goodness of the algorithm using Mathematica:

```
AllTrue[Select[Range[START_VALUE, LAST_VALUE, 2], Mod[2# - 1, #] == 1 && Mod[(# - 1)!, #] != 0], PrimeQ]]
```